
On the road: Introduction to the inaugural issue of Psychreg Journal of Psychology

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The editorial team and I are proud to present this very first issue of *Psychreg Journal of Psychology* (PJP), under the aegis of Psychreg – an online resource in psychology, mental health and well-being. We were driven to found PJP by a noticeable lack of journals which are open access and free to publish, and are devoted solely to the study of human behaviour and its allied fields. As an interdisciplinary journal, PJP publishes empirical and theoretical contributions in any of the areas of psychology.

Undeniably, starting a new journal today poses a number of significant challenges and we have no illusions about the effort, time and financial requirement involved in the process. However, we strongly believe that Psychreg, in a short span of time, has evolved into a responsive and thriving community of scholarship. In this inaugural editorial, we outline our vision and passion for PJP, its strengths and challenges, and warmly invite you to support us in our future editions – by submitting manuscripts, reviewing for the journal, or joining the board.

In this very first issue we explore a range of issues in psychology. And we hope you find it intellectually provocative and informative.

We begin by looking at the mental health benefits that people could derive from playing snooker. Rohit Sagoo investigated whether playing snooker sustains development of mental cognition from acquiring and developing knowledge of the game of snooker for the ‘everyday snooker player’ that plays snooker as a hobby or pastime. This work poses an opportunity for further research relating to health and snooker in the future, especially to explore a variety of dimensions associated with snooker from an array of topics that centre on a very broad and holistic scope around issues in health and social care needs of individuals and communities.

Haikel Lima and colleagues sought to initiate a newly developed Personal and Parents’ Parenting Style Scale (PaPPS) to explore the mechanisms of intergenerational transmission between parental parenting

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style and personal parenting style in Asia. Their pioneering work revealed that parental satisfaction and years of parenting did not seem to mediate the transmission; there may perhaps be key cultural differences that require further exploration between both Asian and Western cultures.

The 2nd of April is declared as the World Autism Awareness Day, and to further expand our knowledge on autism, we present an article from John Robert Rilveria which identified the factors involved in the decision-making process of parents regarding the use of psychotropic medicine for their children diagnosed with autism. Integrating both the quantitative and qualitative data led to the formulation of a treatment decision model that explains the interaction of five major variables (child, parent, doctor, decision, and treatment) in the decision-making process from which the parent variable – specifically perception and beliefs towards treatment – directs the decision to use, or not to use such treatment.

Soumen Acharya, Sonia Janice Pilao, and Rona dela Rosa investigate the role of psychosocial variables as correlates and antecedents to depressive symptoms among male adolescents. It further explores the impact of parent-child relationship and cognitive distortion to depressive symptoms. A battery of self-report measures was administered to 150 male adolescents. Regression analysis reveals four variables that were linked to adolescent depression. Their findings suggest that as mothers exert a degree of psychological control, the high-quality parent-child relationship a son share with his father becomes less of a risk for adolescent aggression. Overall, these outcomes support the improvement of access to adolescent mental health services.

Ana Pinto-Coelho assesses the relationship between the need for and use of mental health services in Portugal. The paper particularly explores the complex issues that beset mental health services in the country, along with the factors that potentially contribute to mental health problems. Three discrete predictive factors emerged: (i) sociodemographic; (ii) intercultural contact; and, (iii) psychosocial adjustment. As earlier studies have revealed, these were linked to youth's mental health. Training professionals in a shared care model is theoretically not linked with consistent improvements in the recognition or management of mental health services in Portugal. A mental health service system based on the recovery concept incorporates the services of a community support system organised around the rehabilitation model's description of the impact of severe mental illness.

Mohammad Mosavat and Jean-Luc Vannier present a psychoanalytic commentary about a play recently performed in Tehran, Iran through an interview with its author, Mohammad Mosavat. The co-signatories both attended a performance of this play. Invited by Shahid Behesti, Alzahra, and Shiraz Universities for many public lectures and supervisions, the French psychoanalyst Jean-Luc Vannier signs the commentary while the interview and the translation were conducted by the Iranian psychoanalyst in training at the Freudian Group of Tehran, Mahyar Ali Naghi.

Finally, through an interview, Bruce Cohen of the University of Auckland offers a comprehensive Marxist critique of the business of mental health, demonstrating how the prerogatives of neoliberal capitalism for productive, self-governing citizens have allowed the discourse on mental illness to expand beyond the psychiatric institution into many previously untouched areas of public and private life including the home, school and the workplace.

Once again, we welcome you to our first issue, and we invite you to become a central part of our future issues. Be part of our growth; without you, we will not succeed.